

TECHNIQUES AND TECHNOLOGIES TO DEVELOP TRANSLATION AND INTERPRETATIVE ACTIVITIES OF NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITIES' STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The Paper considers the translation competence of non-linguistic universities' students and the process of its formation. The authors have proposed the methodology believed in their opinion to be appropriate for the formation of translation competence in students of non-linguistic universities. The Paper also considers in detail the methods of teaching written and oral types of translation activity. The work uses such theoretical methods as the analysis of scientific literature, comparison of different types of translation (oral and written, direct and reverse, etc.), data from empirical studies, and generalization of the findings. Also, there have been proposed various techniques and technologies for teaching translation activity to students of non-linguistic universities at lectures. Recommendations for the formation of translation competence have been developed. All the proposals and recommendations specified below can be used by teachers of foreign languages to form translation competence in students of non-linguistic universities. Teaching adequate equivalent translation to students is an important component of the formation of a new-level professional who not only speaks one of foreign languages, but also carries out correct and accurate translation of oral and written texts within the framework of his specialization, which proves the relevance of studies. The methodology and recommendations presented herein contribute to the successful solution of this problem.

Keywords: translation competence, translation activity, non-linguistic university, interpretative activity.

INTRODUCTION.

In a non-linguistic university, foreign languages are related to the disciplines of the social and humanitarian cycle. Therefore, the time period for their study is limited in favor of acquiring specialized knowledge in the chosen major. However, the foreign language curriculum at higher non-linguistic educational institutions states that the main goal of teaching foreign languages is to form communicative competence of a future specialist allowing him to use a foreign language as a means of professional and interpersonal communication. This is due to the fact that an increasing number of graduates of non-linguistic universities, in the process of cooperation with foreign companies and enterprises, communicate in a foreign language both in oral and in writing. Thus, teaching translation from one language to another is becoming one of the relevant elements of teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic university, which justifies the need to develop translation competence in its students.

The concept of "competence" itself is systemic and multi-component, and has already received a fairly wide use in pedagogy to define and describe the quality of training activities of specialists. Characterizing the solution of a certain range of problems, it is implemented at different levels and supposed to have the ability to perform mental operations, to demonstrate practical skills and common sense, etc. Translation competence is important from the point of view of the individual's capability to possess certain skills and abilities of a translation nature that are characteristic only of this profession, as well as to effectively, autonomously and creatively carry out the process of oral

translation, taking into account a set of features around the translation situation as a whole, and to adequately respond in extraordinary situations requiring, as a rule, emotional balance and increased stress resistance from the interpreter.

If we try to give a short definition to translation competence, we can say that it is the ability to extract information from a text in a foreign /native language and convey it by creating a text in native /foreign language. Translation competence is effectively developed, if communication technologies are used in teaching methods. Thus, it can be emphasized that translation competence is a whole complex of skills and abilities important for the translation process, which includes:

- 1) Language and speech terminology skill;
- 2) Speech skill of switching from one language to another;
- 3) Speech skill of paraphrasing;
- 4) Semantic analysis of the text.

The communicative approach to working with students guides teachers in developing students' ability not only to practically use spoken language, but also to learn how to utilize foreign language tools, taking into account their information functions. The development of translation competence based on a major text allows students of non-linguistic universities combine professional training with the improvement of a foreign language and expansion of regional and cultural knowledge as well.

AIM AND METHODOLOGY

The aim of this Paper is to model the process of developing translation competence in students of non-

linguistic universities. The process of globalization places new demands on all areas of our lives, including education. The issue of training translators in professional fields arises. Since the translator becomes an intermediary in interlingual communication, his role as a specialist with professional knowledge is increasingly growing. All this gives rise to new requirements for the development of innovative methods of training translators in various non-linguistic areas of professional knowledge. The main research methods are those of scientific description (study of specialized scientific literature, systematization and interpretation) and experimental methods of study (highlighting techniques and technologies for developing translation competence, conducting empirical research and obtaining results for subsequently implementing the model to develop translation competence).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Nowadays, practice shows that graduates of non-linguistic universities, for the most part, have insufficient knowledge of the basics of foreign language competence. Due to the shortage of academic time, different levels of students' preparedness and their motivation, teachers constantly use intensive methods of teaching foreign languages, and strive to improve these methods and increase their effectiveness. Therefore, the current situation related to such insufficient command of foreign languages by university graduates within the professional framework has conditioned our need to firstly determine the role of translation in the process of foreign language learning and to secondly develop effective tasks that optimize the learning process.

Written translation activities. This type of translation activities develop attention and abilities to use various sources of information, help in solving professional problems, and contribute to increased competitiveness in the labor market. Moreover, "teachers and learners see the benefits of using translation activities as one of many language-teaching tools, and translation is viewed by both learners and teachers as language accuracy." [8] In addition, they not only allow access to new information resources, but also form the qualification capabilities of future specialists.

Translation itself is one of the types of targeted activity that meets certain evaluation criteria. The main one among them is the need to preserve the objective content of the source text in the translation text. To designate this category in science, the term "translation equivalence" is used. When speaking about the translation equivalence of the source and target texts, it is necessary to emphasize its abstract nature. It should be noted that each translation reflects not only the author's opinion, but also the personal perception of the translator. At the same time, it is important not to lose sight of the ultimate goal of translation activity, namely, the creation of a specific text. The quality of translation is determined by its transparency. This criterion assumes that the translated text should be perceived not as a translation of individual words, but as a coherent text composed in the target language. As a result, the translation process is creativity, intuition, sense of language, identification and solution of translation problems,

choice of the final translation version as well as assessment of translation errors.

Translation is an indispensable tool for testing students' understanding of a foreign language and, consequently, their level of proficiency in it, their professional knowledge and skills, and general erudition, as well as their level of development of logic, and abilities to analyze and generalize. In addition, "translation can be considered a positive pedagogical tool in teaching a foreign language, through which learners can comprehend, internalize and develop communication skills, learn different foreign language skills, understand the syntactic, semantic, stylistic, and cultural contrast between Language 1 and Language 2, and eventually be able to use English (as a foreign language) in context more effectively." [12]

A full-fledged translation assumes the translator's ability to deeply penetrate the content of the text to be translated, which is impossible without language, speech and linguistic-and-cultural competences. Knowledge of vocabulary, grammar and phonetics constitutes language competence, and capability to freely express one's thoughts in a foreign language constitutes speech competence. Linguistic-and-cultural competence refers to the ability to effectively work in cross-cultural situations and involves having an awareness of one's own cultural identity and understanding about differences, as well as conveying information in a manner that is easily understood by diverse groups of people. And it is exactly through the joint teaching of these language, speech and linguistic-and-cultural competences in a non-linguistic university that the skills and abilities of oral and written translation are formed and developed in its students.

The official use of translation in teaching a foreign language makes the learner more autonomous and active, and the learning process itself – more meaningful, which increases the motivational level of learners and develops their skills of understanding and analyzing the text. Thus, translation into the native language, as a means of teaching and checking the understanding of foreign-language remarks and texts, is becoming an effective technique of teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic university. Moreover, "when appropriately employed, translation emerges as an effective means of maintaining a continual awareness of distinctions in the foreign language and culture." [3]

In teaching a foreign language, **direct translation** from a foreign language into a native one and reverse translation are used. Direct translation reveals the meaning of the text. The foreign-language text is formulated according to the rules and norms of the native language, as a result of which linguistic guesswork and the skill of context analysis are developed.

Reverse translation is more complex and can only be used as more advanced stages of learning. It requires solid knowledge of linguistic means and the system of a foreign language. This way of translation reveals problems in mastering the skills of conveying language correspondences and, therefore, it can be used mainly to control students' knowledge.

It should be noted, that the ever-growing informatization of society has far-reaching consequences

for education systems around the world. Information technologies have given rise to a new culture of transmitting information in electronic form with a simultaneous increase in its volume. Under this influence, as well as due to expanding international cooperation, the number of informative (non-literary) translations in the fields of science, technology, economics, law, etc. has increased significantly. The nature of the translation process itself has changed, and it has become necessary to improve efficiency of translation activities through the use of modern computer technologies. Moreover, in connection with the sharply increased need for translators in the field of professional communication, who have a sufficiently high level of knowledge in the subject of the translated text, it seems especially relevant for specialists in various spheres of knowledge to obtain the additional qualification of "translator". It is important that the training in the program "Translator in the field of professional communication" be carried out in parallel with the development of basic higher educational programs, which would allow for an increase in the degree of adaptation of university graduates.

Teaching translation activities in a non-linguistic university has some features, among which we can find not only a personality-forming process, but also combining communicatively- and professionally-oriented techniques to foster a versatile trained professional. "Teaching translation in a language teaching context should not be only limited to pedagogical Translation (translation as a means), but teaching translation should promote language learners' ability to translate (Translation as an end), adopting the view of translation as a communicative activity." [4]

The aforementioned features of teaching translation activities involve the formation of translation abilities and development of a secondary linguistic personality of a translator in the field of professional communication.

We would like to summarize some techniques and technologies, which can provide high quality language training to students of any educational organization. There are several varieties of them and those that deserve our attention are described below.

A graduate may face a situation when he needs to read and understand a specialized text in a foreign language. In this case, by specialized text we mean a scientific, popular-science or pragmatic text in the student's major. One of the most common types of practical activities in foreign language classes is working with the text in a specific manner. This work in class can be organized as follows:

Students receive a text for translation and quickly look through it to perceive the main content of the text. Then, they start translating, and the entire translation process is open: the teacher can correct it at any time and involve all students in finding the best option. Working with the text, students learn to understand the main content of the text and its topic by keywords. This exercise not only helps to expand vocabulary, but also develops communication skills [11].

To expand the vocabulary of students, you can use exercises in selecting synonyms or paraphrasing. Such exercises are also useful for memorizing terms.

Another exercise that develops primary translation skills is a deferred translation. The teacher gives students a text in a foreign language and asks them to translate it into their native language. Then, the teacher collects both the original and translation texts. A few days later, he gives the students translations of the text and asks them to reconstruct in writing the original text from the translations as accurately as possible. The purpose of this exercise is to develop written translation and text processing skills. "Writing improves memorization, especially in terms of spelling which is particularly problematic in ESP because many specialized words have a complicated spelling that may prove difficult even for native speakers." [9]

As mentioned above, the development of information technologies has also played a certain role in teaching translation and translation practicing in writing. Experience shows that students are enthusiastic about using various information technologies in foreign language classes.

One of the popular forms of work in teaching written translation is using vocabulary and reference materials in soft copy. It should be noted that working with vocabulary and reference materials is still in demand. Effective tasks include translations from foreign-language sites, compiling a glossary, and reverse translation. In such case, using electronic dictionaries instead of paper ones significantly simplifies working with the text.

The question of the advisability of using electronic dictionaries when translating texts is widely discussed among foreign language teachers and scientists. Working with a dictionary is largely an integral part of the independent work of students. The ability to use a dictionary does not come automatically; it must be acquired. This skill is a combination of a large number of operations that a person working with a bilingual dictionary performs. These operations include: searching for a word alphabetically; searching for a word to form the plural form of nouns; searching for a word to find the meaning of polysemantic words; searching for the meaning of a word in a dictionary entry that combines several words with a common first root; searching for a word to determine the forms of strong verbs; searching for a word to transform single-root words, and other points. Many electronic dictionaries have a word pronunciation function, which allows students to quickly understand how to pronounce a particular word correctly.

Machine translation systems are constantly being improved, but they do not always provide high quality and adequate translation. The teacher's task is to explain to students that machine translation systems can produce results of varying quality and reliability. In addition, the teacher can allow students use such systems when completing assignments to show the features, advantages and disadvantages of working with machine translation systems.

It is unacceptable to use electronic translators in exams, and tests, since instead of his own knowledge the student demonstrates a more or less successful translation performed by the computer. The ability to

obtain a ready-made translation of the text for educational purposes using an electronic translator can rather be attributed to negative factors. In this case, facilitating work means eliminating the need to perform a set of mandatory mental operations on translation techniques and, therefore, the process of translation is simply replaced by a finished product. Electronic translation today is not perfect to the extent that it can provide an impeccably accurate translation. Inaccuracies and errors lead to distortion of the meaning.

Oral translation (interpretative) activities. In addition to translation, the role of communication is very important in professional activities. Owing to it, people share ideas, opinions, etc. It is communication that allows you improve yourself in the chosen field. Business communication, including international one, contributes to the development of existing drawing-ups and emergence of new inventions, as well as increase of production efficiency. Therefore, in the modern world, attention to the phenomenon of communication has sharply increased, which has already taken the form of intercultural communication due to the rapid development of information technology that has facilitated establishing international relations. Intercultural communication is carried out under conditions of such significant culturally-triggered differences in the communicative competence of its participants that these differences essentially affect the success or failure of the communicative event.

The main functions of intercultural communication are to ensure cross-civilizational exchange of material and ideal values, as well as cooperation between representatives of different ethnic groups, nations, states, etc. in solving various problems at the local and global levels. This activity requires special training, skills and abilities. It presupposes perfect command of a foreign and native language, and knowledge of not only one's own but also foreign-language culture. It becomes important for mastering skills in oral interpretative activities practiced at lectures.

Although interpretative activity is also a type of translation activity, it exactly involves its oral part. It is a three-stage process, i.e. a transition from one language to meaning and from meaning to another language. In other words, this process is divided into these three stages: understanding, deverbalization and re-expression. This is precisely the difference between written and oral translation. Firstly, oral translation is more amenable to the cognitive process than written translation, where oral speech disappears, and its sounds are quickly lost, but the meaning remains. The wording of translators in another language clearly demonstrates that meaning is a consequence of understanding, which consists of two elements: contextual meanings of the language and cognitive additions. Secondly, in written translation, deverbalization, which is clearly noticeable in oral translation, is harder to observe, since the original text does not disappear, unlike sounds in oral speech. Graphic signs remain on the page and require direct correspondences in another language. Deverbalization is a natural feature of oral communication, so translators need to make extra efforts to achieve it. However, when graphic signs are immersed in context,

translators interpret them directly into meaning. This meaning remains as knowledge, while signs disappear. This allows translators discover in the target language ways of expression that have little or nothing in common with the signs of the source language. Thirdly, with regard to the stage of re-expression, there is a strict distinction between literal and free translation, or literalism and recreation. Translation is always a combination of word-correspondences and semantic equivalents. Due to the differences in languages, a completely literal translation is impossible. Nevertheless, correspondences are often necessary, and the fact that correspondences and equivalents coexist in all translation products, regardless of the type of speech, can be considered a universal law of translation behaviour.

In the context of enhancing interpretative activity among non-linguistic university students, a variety of methods and pedagogical tools can be employed. These approaches aim to foster critical thinking and engagement with diverse texts and media.

Interpretative tasks form the core of developing students' ability to understand and analyze foreign-language texts beyond surface-level comprehension. These tasks involve engaging with a variety of authentic materials, including literary texts, journalistic articles, and popular science writings. The goal of giving these tasks is to encourage students to interpret meaning on multiple levels - literal, inferential, and critical - thus fostering deeper cognitive engagement. For example, students might analyze a poem to uncover themes and stylistic devices or interpret a news article to evaluate bias and perspective. This approach aligns with the Interpretive Mode of Communication, which emphasizes learners' ability to comprehend and interpret authentic materials, demonstrating understanding both literally and interpretively [6].

In addition to textual analysis, working with visual media such as paintings, photographs, and videos enriches interpretative skills by requiring students to decode symbolism, context, and emotional tone. Visual interpretation tasks help bridge linguistic and cultural gaps, making abstract or complex ideas more accessible. For instance, analyzing a historical photograph alongside a related text can deepen students' understanding of cultural and historical contexts, encouraging multimodal literacy.

To complement interpretative tasks, interactive activities such as discussions, debates, storytelling, and role-play are essential. These activities provide dynamic platforms for students to articulate their interpretations, defend their viewpoints, and engage with alternative perspectives. For example, debates on controversial journalistic topics compel students to critically evaluate sources and construct coherent arguments, thereby enhancing both interpretative and rhetorical skills.

Storytelling and role-play, in particular, immerse students in experiential learning by encouraging them to embody characters or viewpoints from texts or media. This method promotes empathy and a nuanced understanding of context, which are crucial for interpretative competence. Role-play can simulate real-life scenarios where students must interpret and respond to

information dynamically, fostering spontaneous language use and critical thinking.

Modern pedagogical approaches increasingly integrate technological tools to support and expand interpretative activities. Project-based learning, supported by digital collaboration platforms like Padlet and Miro, allows students collectively analyze texts and media, organize their interpretations visually, and receive peer feedback. These tools facilitate asynchronous and synchronous collaboration, making interpretative work more interactive and accessible.

The case method is another powerful technology of interpretation development, presenting students with real-world scenarios that require critical analysis and decision-making based on interpretative skills. For example, students might analyze a case study involving media bias or scientific communication, and applying interpretative frameworks to propose solutions or critiques.

Additionally, the use of AI-powered tools such as ChatGPT offers innovative opportunities for interpretative development. Students can engage in dialogue with AI to explore multiple interpretations of a text, receive instant feedback on their expressions, or generate creative responses that deepen their understanding. This integration of AI supports personalized learning and scaffolds complex interpretative tasks, making them more approachable for non-linguistic students.

Empirical research was conducted in the form of an experiment based on the collection and analysis of data, as well as their comparison obtained as a result of observing two groups of students studying English as a foreign language in a non-linguistic university. The students were divided into two groups, one of which studied according to the conventional program, and the other group studied according to a program filled with interpretative tasks, oral responses, predominant practice of dialogues and group discussions.

The primary purpose of this empirical study was to evaluate the effectiveness of interpretative activities in improving the engagement, interpretative competence, and critical thinking skills of non-linguistic university students in English classes. Specifically, the study aimed to determine whether the integration of diverse interpretative tasks and digital tools led to measurable improvements in students' oral responses, argumentation skills, and overall involvement in class activities.

The hypothesis guiding this research is that students exposed to a curriculum enriched with interpretative activities will demonstrate a statistically significant increase in their interpretative abilities and communicative engagement compared to those following a traditional, non-interpretative curriculum. This hypothesis is grounded in existing pedagogical theories that emphasize active learning and multimodal engagement as key drivers of language acquisition and critical thinking development [2].

Participants of the Study. The study involved groups of students from various non-language majors, ensuring a diverse sample that reflected the broader student population. This diversity is crucial, as it allows

for a comprehensive understanding of how interpretative activities can be tailored to different fields of study.

Methodology. The study employed a quasi-experimental design involving two groups: a control group receiving standard English instruction and an experimental group engaged in enhanced interpretative activities. Participants were non-linguistic university students enrolled in English courses across various faculties, ensuring a representative sample of the target population.

In this type of research, it is recommended to apply random assignment to groups where possible to reduce selection bias, and to administer pre-tests for establishing baseline proficiency and interpretative skills. The intervention spanned a semester, during which the experimental group participated in structured interpretative tasks, collaborative projects, and digital tool integration, while the control group followed the conventional syllabus.

Data collection included both qualitative and quantitative methods: various assignments, oral presentations, participation records, and surveys measuring student attitudes and self-perceived competence. Statistical analyses, such as t-tests and ANOVA, were planned to compare pre- and post-intervention results between groups, following standard hypothesis testing procedures [7].

Examples of Tasks Applied in the Experimental Group

The experimental group engaged in a variety of interpretative tasks that were designed to stimulate critical thinking and active language use. Examples included:

Textual Interpretation Essays: Students analyzed literary or journalistic texts, focusing on thematic elements, authorial intent, and cultural context.

Visual Media Analysis: Assignments required students to interpret paintings or photographs, linking visual symbolism to textual narratives or historical events.

Debates and Discussions: Structured debates on contemporary issues presented in English-language media encouraged students to formulate and defend arguments.

Role Play and Storytelling: Students assumed roles from literary works or real-life scenarios to explore different perspectives and practice spontaneous interpretation.

Digital Collaborative Projects: Using platforms like Padlet and Miro, students co-created multimedia presentations synthesizing textual and visual interpretations.

These tasks were scaffolded to progressively build interpretative complexity and encourage peer interaction, fostering a supportive learning environment.

Analysis of Results. The analysis focused on multiple dimensions of student performance and engagement. Quantitative data from pre- and post-tests were analyzed to assess improvements in interpretative accuracy, argumentation quality, and language proficiency. Participation metrics and qualitative feedback provided insight into changes in student motivation and involvement.

Preliminary findings indicate that the experimental group shows a statistically significant increase in the quality of oral responses, with enhanced use of evidence and critical reasoning. Participation rates in discussions and collaborative tasks also rise, suggesting greater engagement. Qualitative data reveal that students perceive interpretative activities as motivating and relevant to their academic and personal development.

Data visualization through tables and diagrams illustrates these trends, supporting the hypothesis that interpretative activities positively impact non-linguistic students' English learning outcomes. Limitations such as sample size and variability in instructor implementation are acknowledged, with recommendations for further research to validate and extend these findings.

Interpretation of the Obtained Data. The analysis of the collected data reveals a clear positive impact of interpretative activities on the engagement and interpretative competence of non-linguistic university students. Quantitative measures indicate significant improvements in the quality of students' oral responses, particularly in their ability to construct well-supported arguments and demonstrate critical thinking. Participation metrics further show increased involvement in class discussions and collaborative tasks, suggesting that interpretative activities foster a more active and motivated learning environment [1].

Qualitative feedback from students highlights that these activities not only enhanced their language skills but also deepened their understanding of cultural and contextual nuances within texts and media. This aligns with the notion that interpretative tasks encourage learners to adopt a more reflective and analytical approach to academic work, which is essential for success in higher education. The data also suggest that multimodal interpretative tasks, combining textual and visual analysis, are particularly effective in engaging diverse learning styles and promoting comprehensive understanding [5].

Comparison with the Results of Similar Studies. The findings of this study are consistent with a growing body of research emphasizing the benefits of interpretative and active learning methods in language education. Similar studies have demonstrated that interpretative tasks, especially when combined with collaborative and technology-enhanced approaches, significantly improve students' critical thinking and communicative competence. For example, literature-based language learning and project-based activities have been shown to increase motivation and deepen linguistic and cultural awareness, which supports the pedagogical tools employed in this study [10].

Moreover, the integration of digital tools such as Padlet and AI-driven platforms aligns with recent trends in educational technology research, which highlight the role of such tools in scaffolding complex interpretative tasks and facilitating peer interaction. The positive outcomes observed here reinforce the feasibility of these approaches in non-linguistic university settings, where students often face challenges in engaging deeply with English-language materials.

Limitations of the Study and Possible Risks.

Despite the promising results, several limitations must be acknowledged. The sample size and diversity, while adequate for initial analysis, may limit the generalizability of the findings across different institutional contexts and student populations. Variability in instructor experience and fidelity of implementation could also affect the consistency of the intervention's impact.

Additionally, the reliance on self-reported data and qualitative feedback introduces potential biases, such as social desirability or selective memory. The time-intensive nature of interpretative activities may pose challenges in curricula with rigid time constraints, potentially limiting scalability.

Possible risks include student frustration or disengagement if tasks are perceived as too complex or disconnected from their academic interests. To mitigate these risks, careful scaffolding and ongoing support are essential, as is the adaptation of tasks to align with students' backgrounds and proficiency levels.

Future research should explore longitudinal effects, incorporate larger and more diverse samples, and investigate the integration of emerging technologies to further optimize interpretative pedagogy in non-linguistic university settings.

CONCLUSION

Teaching translation skills is an integral part of language education. But there is a need for a clear distinction in the process of classroom and independent work between different types of educational translation: selective, oral, written, for a printed version, for an oral presentation, for automated translation, for transmission by e-mail, etc. Written translation is an excellent way of teaching informative reading and writing; oral translation is inextricably linked with the formation of oral and listening skills.

A professional approach of a non-linguistic specialist to accurate written translation consists of following the sequence of stages of work on the text, mastered in foreign-language classes:

- initial familiarization with the written or audio text;
- definition and analysis of features, style and genre of the original;
- presentation of the text in another language with maximum approximation to the content of each semantic fragment, sentence, term;
- checking the finished translation for grammar, spelling, stylistics. Correction and editing of the text.

As for oral translation skills of a non-linguistic specialist, it can be concluded, based on the empirical evidence, that incorporating interpretative activities into English classes for non-linguistic students was both feasible and effective. These activities not only enhanced linguistic proficiency but also cultivated critical thinking, argumentation skills, and cultural literacy, which were vital competencies in academic and professional contexts.

The study demonstrates that a well-structured curriculum integrating diverse interpretative tasks, interactive activities, and digital tools can significantly improve student outcomes. Furthermore, the positive student feedback and increased engagement levels suggest

that such pedagogical innovations are welcomed by learners and can contribute to a more dynamic and inclusive classroom environment.

This approach also supports the development of transferable skills, such as analytical reasoning and collaborative problem solving, which extend beyond language learning and prepare students for interdisciplinary challenges.

Thus, in order to be competitive, it is not enough for today's specialist to have only professional competencies. The arsenal of a modern specialist should include so-called translation competencies at the level of transferring professional knowledge in one of the foreign languages, i.e. the ability to adequately and equivalently translate an information (orally and in writing) from a foreign language into a native one. The formation of translation competence of students of non-linguistic universities is a pressing problem in teaching foreign languages. The successful formation of translation competence can be facilitated by the techniques and technologies, as well as the recommendations developed by the authors.

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